

Title

Digitalisation of Clinical Practice Guidelines: A scoping review with a focus on tools, methods and experiences

Contributors

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Abstract

Objectives

Clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) are essential for evidence-based care, yet their traditional static format limits integration into digital workflows. To date, numerous initiatives have sought to convert CPGs into computer-interpretable guidelines (CIGs). This scoping review maps research on CPG digitalisation and highlights methodological issues and challenges.

Methods

We searched Ovid MEDLINE, Web of Science Core Collection, PMC Europe and Google Scholar for articles published from 01/2014 to 06/2024. We included scientific articles addressing (1) the development and dissemination of digital, evidence-based CPGs, (2) the digitalisation of existing CPGs, and (3) related methodological and technical issues as well as experiences and attitudes of guideline developers and users. Titles/abstracts were screened in duplicate, switching to single-screener mode after 61.5 %. Full texts were screened in duplicate. Data was extracted by one reviewer and double-checked by another.

Results

From 14,357 unique records, 122 studies met eligibility; 84 primarily addressed CIG development and 38 clinical decision support systems implementation, with our focus lying on articles addressing CIGs. Among those, knowledge-representation and formalisation work (30 studies) as well as deployment and evaluation approaches (30 studies) predominated. Recurrent challenges included ambiguous or contradictory source CPGs, terminology-mapping issues, a need for clinician-knowledge-engineer collaboration and integration with other IT systems.

Discussion

This review documents substantial progress in CPG digitalisation – particularly in formal models, standards adoption, and prototype tools – but also reveals challenges that compromise integration into clinical workflows.

Conclusion

To facilitate digitally enabled, interoperable guidelines, present challenges should be addressed through coordinated methodological research, interdisciplinary collaboration, and implementation-focused studies.

Key Messages

What is already known on this topic

Clinical practice guidelines are traditionally published as static documents. In recent years, there has been growing effort to render guidelines into digital, computer-interpretable format.

What this study adds

We provide an overview of the current state of research and published experiences on the digitalisation of clinical practice guidelines.

How this study might affect research, practice or policy

Results of this scoping review offer a starting point for further research, such as on standardisation (core terminologies, interoperable data models) and multidisciplinary collaboration. They underpin initiatives aimed at digitalising clinical guidelines, guideline registries or living-guideline pipelines and inform policy on guideline digitalisation.

INTRODUCTION

Clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) are essential for promoting evidence-based care, enhancing healthcare quality, and improving patient outcomes¹, yet their uptake is often limited and remain challenging: Barriers include, e.g., lack of knowledge and skills related to CPG use, organisational factors, but also CPG characteristics such as a lack of practicability and user-friendliness.² Traditional CPGs are typically published as static text documents, hindering integration with digital workflows and clinical decision support systems (CDSS).³ Consequently, there is a need for digitalisation strategies that render CPGs computable, interoperable, and actionable at the point of care³. Moreover, CPGs should be part of an evidence ecosystem and, ideally, a learning health system which enables continuous updates and seamless clinical integration.⁴

Over the past years, there has been growing emphasis on converting traditional, text-based CPGs into computer-interpretable guidelines (CIGs).⁵ Boxwala et al.⁶ defined four levels of guideline knowledge, reflecting increasing levels of formalisation and computability: Level 1 (unstructured / narrative) represents narrative CPGs in their traditional form, as originally authored by guideline committees; level 2 (semi-structured) consists of organised text but not yet coded information; level 3 (structured) is a computable representation of recommendations including, e.g., conditional logic; level 4 (executable) reflects guideline knowledge that is structured for use within a CDSS.^{6,7} Over the past decades, numerous approaches have been developed and proposed to support the process of representing CPGs in a computer-interpretable way, including model-based approaches such as, e.g. the HL7 Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) standard, among others.⁵

The Association of the Scientific Medical Societies in Germany (AWMF; <https://www.awmf.org>) coordinates the development of the majority of CPGs in Germany. The AWMF-CPG registry (<https://register.awmf.org/de/start>) comprises over 850 CPGs. Most AWMF-CPGs are only available as comprehensive PDF documents, resulting in the disadvantages mentioned above. Therefore, AWMF and partners launched the “Dissolve-E” Project (“Digitalisation of the AWMF guideline registry for an open, guideline-based, trustworthy evidence ecosystem”)⁸. To guide and inform Dissolve-E as well as similar efforts in this field, we conducted the present scoping review.

Our aim is to provide a comprehensive overview of published findings on the development and dissemination of CPGs, including methodological issues and challenges, as well as experiences and attitudes of users and developers.

METHODS

We conducted a scoping review following the guidelines of the JBI (<https://jbi.global/scoping-review-network>). Reporting complies with the PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) statement (<https://www.prisma-statement.org>).

Protocol and registration

The protocol of this review was registered with OSF prior to the start of the screening in July 2024 (<https://osf.io/nf3w7/registrations>). There were few changes to the protocol, which are listed in Supplement 1.

Eligibility criteria

Eligibility criteria followed the Population, Concept, and Context (PCC) framework. The concept in this review are digital evidence-based CPGs and their development.

“Digitalisation” was defined using Boxwala et al.’s⁶ four layers framework described in the introduction. All four layers were considered for this review. Detailed eligibility criteria are outlined in Table 1.

To build on prior research and to capture the most relevant and recent developments, we included only studies published from 2014 onwards. Since many CDSS articles were outdated or lacked detail on digitalisation, we restricted inclusion of CDSS-focused articles to those published from 2020 onward.

Table 1. Eligibility criteria for this scoping review

Population	No limitations; i.e. we included literature from all medical fields	
Concept	<p>Inclusion:</p> <p>Articles with a focus on...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ digital evidence-based CPG development and dissemination ○ digitalisation of existing (narrative) CPG ○ methodological / technical considerations and issues related to the digitalisation of CPGs ○ experiences and attitudes of guideline developers and users (e.g. clinicians) related to digital CPGs 	<p>Exclusion:</p> <p>Articles with a focus on...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ decision aids / tools for patients / for shared decision making ○ clinical decision support systems (CDSS) that were not primarily based on CPGs ○ evaluation in clinical setting / with clinical outcomes (e.g. impact on patient mortality) ○ CDSS published <2020
Context	No limitations; i.e. we included literature from any country and setting	
Further criteria	<p>Inclusion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Full scientific articles published from 2014 onwards, including peer-reviewed and preprint articles ○ Primary research without restrictions on study design ○ Articles in English or German 	<p>Exclusion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Study protocols, abstracts and posters (due to their limited information content) ● Systematic/scoping/mapping reviews and similar review articles (due to our focus on primary research) ● Articles in other languages than English and German (due to feasibility reasons)

Information sources and search strategy

We performed a systematic literature search in the following bibliographic databases from 2014 onwards to 19th of June 2024: Ovid MEDLINE, Web of Science Core Collection, and PMC Europe (Preprints only). Additionally, we searched Google Scholar (first 200 hits sorted by relevance). The search strategies were peer-reviewed and adapted for each information source based on database-specific syntax and controlled vocabulary. Search results were deduplicated using Deduklick (<https://www.risklick.ch/deduklick>) and Covidence (<https://www.covidence.org>) (with manual review). We used EndNote (<https://endnote.com>) for reference management. Search strategies for all databases are presented in Supplement 2.

Study selection

We conducted a pilot screening where the screening team screened the same 25 randomly selected titles/abstracts and discussed their eligibility. Titles/abstracts were then screened independently by two reviewers using Covidence. Discrepancies were resolved by consensus or discussion with a third reviewer. We used the Covidence “most relevant” algorithm to prioritise the studies according to their supposed relevance based on the previous screening decisions. Due to the high number of references, we decided to switch to a single screener mode for the title/abstract screening after 61.5 % (n = 8.832) of references had been screened in duplicate. Full text screening was conducted independently in pairs, with discrepancies resolved as for title/abstract screening.

Data charting process

A data extraction Microsoft Excel template was developed and finalised after pilot testing. Data were extracted by one reviewer (MT) and checked by another (FH, MH, AEM). Discrepancies were resolved by consensus or discussion with a third reviewer.

Data extracted included bibliographic reference, country of origin, type of source, main aim, key methods and findings, tools/technical standards/software studied, topics of the used guidelines, limitations, information on conflicts of interest and funding sources.

Because our scoping review focuses on the digitalisation process of CPGs, we extracted only basic key information for articles focusing on CDSS (including bibliographic information, main aim and key findings).

Data summary and synthesis

Based on the content of the included articles, we developed the following four categories and assigned each study to one of them, considering their main focus: knowledge representation and formalisation; tools and technical implementation; deployment and evaluation; overarching meta level.

Results were narratively summarised, with some of the most relevant results being presented using summarising tables and figures. As usual for scoping reviews, we did not perform a critical appraisal of included studies.

RESULTS

Results of the search

A total of 14,357 unique records were screened for eligibility, with 273 records screened at full text level. We included 122 studies (reported in 130 articles) in this review. The screening process is illustrated in Figure 1. A list of the included studies is available in Supplement 3, a list of excluded studies at full text level with reasons for exclusion in Supplement 4.

Eighty-four of the included articles had a CIG focus and 38 focused primarily on CDSS. A summary of the main aim and methods of the 38 articles about CDSS can be found on OSF (<https://osf.io/nf3w7>). Below, we describe the characteristics and results of the 84 articles on CIG in more detail.

Figure 1. PRISMA 2020 flow chart of the study selection process.

* further information provided on OSF (<https://osf.io/nf3w7>).

Characteristics of included studies

Included articles were mainly full journal articles (n=62), 21 were conference papers and one was a preprint article. Canada was the country where most studies were conducted (n=9), followed by Spain, UK and the USA (n=8, respectively), Germany (n=7), Italy (n=6), and Austria and Israel (n=5, respectively). Authors of 48 articles reported non-commercial funding, of five articles no external funding, of four articles commercial funding and for 27 articles, no information on funding sources was provided. Potential conflicts of interest (CoI) were reported by authors of nine articles, no CoI by authors of 31 articles, and 44 articles provided no information on CoI.

Many of the included studies reported either specific CPGs or the medical topic of the CPGs they worked with. The medical areas most frequently covered were Heart & Circulation (n=26), Cancer (n=20), Endocrine & Metabolic (n=18), Lungs & Airways (n=13), and Infectious Diseases (n=12). Further details on the included articles can be accessed on OSF (<https://osf.io/nf3w7>).

Overview of content related to digitalisation of CPG

An overview of the main aim, methods, and key results of each study is given in Supplement 5. We have assigned the included studies to four categories, as summarised in Table 2. A brief summary of the content of the categories with examples is provided below.

Table 2. Overview of the four categories of studies.

Category	Number of studies assigned	Content
1. Knowledge Representation and Formalisation	30	Method, model, or framework for transforming data or narrative knowledge into computable, structured formats
2. Tools and Technical Implementation	14	Building actual software for working with CIGs, i.e. tools for creating them, systems for running them, interfaces for displaying them, or platforms for managing them
3. Deployment and Evaluation	30	Empirical evidence about implementing CIG systems in real or simulated clinical environments, or evaluating their performance and usability
4. Overarching Meta-Level	10	Guidance, frameworks, methodologies, or empirical insights about the process of developing, implementing, or adopting CIGs

1. Knowledge Representation and Formalisation:

Articles assigned to this category focused, e.g. on formal languages and logic, ontologies and semantic models, data extraction and natural language processing, standards and specifications. E.g., Lichtner et al.⁹ proposed a FHIR-based computable format for evidence-based guideline artifacts. Wilk et al.¹⁰ proposed a framework based on first-order logic (FOL)

to combine multiple discordant CPGs and patient preferences. And Fux et al.¹¹ developed a layered approach to facilitate customisation and maintenance of CIGs specified in the PROforma formalism.

2. Tools and Technical Implementation

Articles reported, e.g., on authoring and development tools, execution engines, visualisation and simulation, technical architectures, platforms, or infrastructure for CIG management, proof-of-concept systems or prototypes that show technical feasibility. Fortmann et al.¹², e.g., developed a system for dynamic visualisation of CPGs that incorporates the individual patient’s current treatment context. And Bottrighi and Terenziani¹³ presented a “shell” to facilitate the formalism-based design and development of new CIG systems (or update an existing one).

3. Deployment and Evaluation

Assigned articles reported on, e.g., end-to-end implementations, real-world deployments, experience reports, surveys, interviews, and evaluation of systems. E.g., Javan Amoli¹⁴ interviewed managers of cancer screening about an electronic risk assessment system as a tool for the prevention of cancer. Zamborlini et al.¹⁵ built a reusable, rule-based system that detects interactions among recommendations coming from various guidelines in the context of multimorbidity and tested it in a case study on rehabilitation of breast-cancer patients. Khorikian-Ghazari et al.¹⁶ explored the attitudes toward a living guideline implemented in the MAGICapp among health professionals.

Of the 30 articles in this category, 20 contained one or more types of evaluation methods (as indicated in Table 3). Key findings from evaluations from those 20 studies are summarised in Supplement 6.

Table 3. Evaluation methods applied in 20 of the 30 articles assigned to the category “Deployment and evaluation”.

	Evaluations (n) involving clinicians	Evaluations (n) involving methodologists/ authors themselves	Evaluations (n) involving both groups
Working on case studies	1	5	1
Qualitative methods (focus groups, interviews, think-aloud method)	3		1
Survey	1		
Survey & qualitative methods	2		1
Feedback (unstructured)	1		1
Analysis of user data	2		
Randomised controlled trial	1		

4. Overarching Meta-Level

Articles assigned to this category reported, e.g., on guideline development processes or evaluation frameworks and methodologies on a superordinate level, rather than contributing a specific representation, tool, or deployment. E.g., Michaels et al.^{3 17} presented a multidisciplinary “Kaizen” approach aimed at developing methods to improve CPG development, implementation, and evaluation. Iglesias et al.¹⁸ analysed rule formalisms for representing CPGs to facilitate the selection of suitable rule-based technologies for modelling knowledge from CPGs for CDSS. Two articles explored general attitudes of CPG users towards using CIG. They identified factors influencing physicians’ intention to use CIGs, i.e. attitudes toward using CIGs, organisational support, perceived usefulness of CIGs and social influence (e.g. attitudes of colleagues or supervisors)¹⁹, and barriers to the use of CPGs in digital form, i.e., lack of access to computers, need to buy phone credit, need for training and fear of increased workload.²⁰

Issues and challenges

Below, we briefly describe the main challenges that have been reported and dealt with in the included studies, some of which are also interrelated. We illustrate them with examples from the studies.

Ambiguity, contradictions and incompleteness in source CPGs:

Translating CPGs into computer-interpretable formats was sometimes hampered by vague terms, nested sentences, and missing, redundant or contradictory information in the guideline texts, requiring extra interpretation by clinicians or experts. A possibility to facilitate the translation of CPGs can be the development and use of authoring tools. E.g., Torres et al.²¹ developed an authoring tool for formalising CPGs into CIGs, explicitly designed to facilitate authoring by clinicians. Also, platforms such as MAGIC/MAGICapp (<https://app.magicapp.org/#/guidelines>) or Openclinical (<https://www.openclinical.net>) have emerged to support authoring, processing and publishing CIGs or clinical pathways.

Conflicting CPGs:

Contradictory information was a particular issue when there were several guidelines on the same topic or in cases of multimorbidity. E.g., Abidi²² addressed this issue by creating a semantic-web-based system which integrates and executes multiple disease-specific CPGs into a unified comorbidity knowledge base. Fdez-Olivares et al.²³ developed a multi-agent planning framework to automatically reconcile multiple disease-specific guidelines, including drug interactions, scheduling constraints, and patient-centered preference, and select the optimal personalised treatment.

Terminology-mapping problems and lack of standardisation:

Issues when using different terminologies such as e.g. SNOMED CT, LOINC or UMLS were described, e.g. failure to find exact terms that match the original CPG terms, missing codes or issues with the coding of acronyms. E.g. Quesada-Martinez et al.²⁴ devised a method that automatically aligns a CIG with existing ontologies to extract relevant clinical terms and reported some mismatches between terms entered and SNOMED CT terms provided. Becker et al.²⁵ reported challenges due to the unavailability of a focused international standard

SNOMED CT in German. When using a translated version, errors in translation and mapping were more likely.

Need for Clinician – knowledge engineer collaboration:

A range of studies have demonstrated that adequate digitisation of CPGs requires both knowledge-engineers skilled in formal representation and clinicians who bring domain expertise, ensuring accuracy and completeness. Authoring tools that enable clinicians without specialised IT skills to create CIGs can offer an alternative.²¹

Integration with other IT systems:

Integrating CIGs with existing IT systems, like hospital information systems, is crucial so that clinicians can use them at the point of care.²⁶ Another important feature is the ability to integrate and process EHR data into a CIG system.²⁷

Other challenges:

Further challenges and issues included, e.g., usability issues, training opportunities for clinicians or automating functions.

Technical standards

The included studies used a broad range of technical standards and tools. Where applicable, we have divided their use into process model, data/representation model and execution engine. PROforma was among the most prevalent process models, followed by BPMN, Drools Rule Language, GLARE, and CPG-on-FHIR. There was also evidence of multi-model usage in some studies (e.g., BPMN combined with PROforma, openEHR GDL, FHIR integration). For data models, FHIR dominated as the modern standard for data exchange, followed by openEHR. Other data/representation models included SNOMED CT, LOINC, and various ontology-based models (e.g., OWL/Protégé). As execution engines, the Tallis engine (for PROforma) was frequently used. Further notable engines were Camunda (for BPMN), Drools Execution Engine, GLARE, Deontics, and META-GLARE.

Figure 2 provides an overview of technical standards, categorised by the year of publication of the articles in which they were applied. Details on process models, data/representation models and execution engines are displayed in Supplement 7. The studies also applied a range of basic standards such as JSON or XML which we have not included in the figure for clarity.

Figure 2. Overview of model usage over time by type.

Models that appeared only once were grouped into the category “Other”. These were as follows: **Process Models:** CDS Hooks, CompGuide ontology, EON, FHIR CIG IG, FHIR PlanDefinition, GLIF, HeD, OWL + SPIN, Prova, RDF, RIF/PRD, SAGE, SHACL, UML, UMLS, openEHR template; **Data/Representation Models:** ACT, CDA HL7, CompGuide, EHRcom, GEM, HL7, ICD-O, IHE XDW, LOD, PROforma, Pathfinder 1, UML; **Execution Engines:** Activiti + Picard, Arden Syntax Engine (via Arden Syntax Server), Arden2ByteCode, BMIR EON Guideline Interpreter system, CDSS Workbench, CompGuide CIG Execution Server, Deontics Engine, Pellet, SWRLTab Protège, TopQuadrant TopBraidComposer, Yakindu statecharts, openEHR-based CDR, u-BRAIN execution engine.

DISCUSSION

This scoping review provides an overview of the current state of research and published experiences on the digitalisation of CPGs. We identified a remarkable number of studies published since 2014 that focus on the transformation of narrative CPGs into computer-interpretable formats, the tools and technical implementations that support this transformation, and the deployment and evaluation of digital guideline systems. We also identified multiple issues and challenges – including ambiguous source CPGs,

terminology-mapping challenges, the need for clinician-knowledge-engineer collaboration, and technical integration of CIGs into hospital information systems. Our findings highlight both the progress that has been made in the past years and the ongoing challenges that hinder widespread adoption.

The broad methodological spectrum of the included studies underscores the multidimensional nature of digital guideline work, ranging from theoretical modelling (e.g., ontologies, FHIR-based artefacts) to concrete software prototypes and practice implementation reports. Predominance of knowledge-representation research contributed novel methods, models or frameworks for converting narrative knowledge into computable formats. The continued interest in formal languages reflects the community's recognition that a solid semantic foundation is a prerequisite for interoperable, reusable digital guidelines.

Particularly with regard to technical standards, there have been significant developments compared to prior reviews from 2013²⁸ and 2023⁵. PROforma and BPMN turned out as the most commonly used workflow/process formalisms while FHIR and openEHR have emerged as most common data standards. Some studies used hybrid approaches or designed their own engines to fit specific research needs. Overall, there may well be a growing trend towards FHIR. E.g., the synergy of CPG-on-FHIR and EBM-on-FHIR⁹ maps the entire evidence ecosystem, encompassing primary studies, meta-analyses, and Evidence-to-Decision frameworks together with the final recommendation logic. Such options facilitate living guideline architectures: new primary data can automatically trigger re-calculations in meta-analyses and refresh evidence-to-decision processes. If this leads to changes in recommendations, these can automatically be realised in the respective CIG. Consequently, manual maintenance of CIG can be eliminated and a timelier alignment of CIG with changes in the underlying evidence processes can be achieved.

Strengths and limitations

The review's major strengths are its systematic, transparent methodology – including peer-reviewed search strategies and a registered protocol – and its broad research scope. This breadth, however, required extensive screening, leading us to adopt certain methodological compromises: We performed single-reviewer screening for the latter half of title/abstract screening and had data extracted by one person and checked by a second. However, based on AI-supported ranking of references in Covidence, the second half was likely the less relevant part of the articles. As with most scoping reviews, we did not perform a formal quality appraisal. Therefore, the robustness of individual primary studies cannot be inferred from our review.

Implications for research and practice

Standardisation and interoperability remain a major topic for further research. One goal would be to further establish a consensus on a core set of terminologies and data models (e.g. FHIR-based guideline artefacts linked to SNOMED CT) that would reduce mapping effort and facilitate reuse between institutions. Also, strategies for reconciling multiple disease-specific guidelines in multimorbid populations as well as combining guidelines on related topics from different sources warrant further investigation.

Multidisciplinary collaboration is vital for future research projects: Collaboration between clinicians, knowledge engineers, and computer scientists is essential to eliminate ambiguities in source guidelines and ensure clinical relevance.

As some of the included studies show, living guideline pipelines are becoming increasingly important. Future studies should take this requirement into account. Ideally, approaches offer fully automated workflows that continuously incorporate new findings and pass on changes to implemented CDSS.

It is noteworthy that, with a few exceptions, the majority of the included studies addressed relatively isolated steps in CIG development. There is a need for successful CPG digitalisation projects, including evaluation and implementation into clinical practice. This is one of the aims of our current project Dissolve-E⁸, which is expected to enrich the research landscape in this area: The project aims at digitalising the AWMF CPG registry which comprises the majority of German CPGs (>850 in total).

Conclusion

This scoping review provides an overview of the rapidly evolving landscape of CPG digitalisation, revealing substantial progress in knowledge representation, tooling, and deployments, while also exposing persistent gaps and issues, e.g. in standardisation and usability. Addressing these through coordinated methodological research, interdisciplinary collaboration, and implementation-focused studies will be crucial to realise the promise of digitally enabled, interoperable guidelines.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

- GL, FvD, and JJM are authors of one paper included in this scoping review.
- JS is the managing director of Howto Health, a company that offers business solutions at the interface between digital technology and the healthcare sector.
- CS is employed by the aQua Institute that develops the digital guideline registry in the Dissolve-E project.
- IM, MN, and IBK are employed by the AWMF which runs the AWMF guideline registry. The AWMF receives membership fees from its professional societies and public funding from the German Federated Committee, the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG), and the Cancer Aid. The AWMF coordinates the Dissolve-E research project.

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ETHICAL APPROVAL STATEMENT

Only secondary data, and no personal data, was collected or processed. Therefore, approval from an ethics committee was not required.

DISCLOSURE OF AI USE

We used the following AI-assistance to prepare this work:

- GPT-OSS 120b via Open WebUI, ChatGPT (version GPT-5) and Claude Sonnet 4 for assistance with data structuring and summarising extracted data,
- GPT-OSS 120b via Open WebUI as a formulation aid for writing the manuscript.

All content generated with the assistance of AI has been critically reviewed by the authors for accuracy and amended where necessary.

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